

Extending intent-powered network management with LMs in B5G infrastructures

Claudia Carballo González*, Sergio Giménez-Antón*, Miquel Tarzán-Lorente*,
Hatim Chergui*, Carolina Fernández-Martínez*

*i2CAT Foundation, Barcelona (Spain)

Abstract—Due to their manual, error-prone, and resource-intensive nature, traditional network management methods become unfeasible for highly dynamic, complex, and heterogeneous Beyond 5G (B5G) systems. In this landscape, Intent-Based Networking (IBN) emerges as a promising solution that automates the service lifecycle while offering flexibility and scalability. Nevertheless, IBN faces challenges in expressing, interpreting, and refining high-level intents across diverse Use Cases (UCs). This work proposes a Language Model Intent-based Application Programming Interface (LM-IbAPI) for enhanced dynamic network management in B5G infrastructures to address these challenges. In the framework of the 6GDIFERENTE project, our solution is seamlessly integrated with the management layer to translate multiple intents from diverse UCs into precise network actions with accuracy and reduced time response. We employed Ollama as a unified framework to quickly and effectively test several language models. The results demonstrated that *mistral_7B* achieved the best trade-off between processing time and accuracy, being capable of generalising across varying numbers of users, services, operators, and South-bound Interfaces (SBIs).

Index Terms—B5G networks, intents, language models, network management, Ollama

I. INTRODUCTION

Beyond 5G (B5G) wireless systems will enable a wide range of advanced applications with very tight quality of service (QoS) requirements, directly impacting the industrial, educational, health and social sectors. To meet these strict requirements, B5G networks must guarantee a three-dimensional ecosystem composed of Terrestrial (TN) and Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) to offer an adequate anywhere and anytime user perception and handle multiple service requests, a massive number of connected devices and different mobility behaviours [1].

Traditional network management becomes unfeasible in this highly complex and ultra-dense heterogeneous environment due to the highly time-consuming, increasing costs and error-prone to generate configurations for each service manually [2]. In contrast, a well-designed management and orchestration framework is required to automate the network configuration, making it easier to coordinate diverse B5G Use Cases (UCs) and dynamically adapt the network to multiple scenarios [3]. In such a context, Intent-Based Networking (IBN) emerges as an essential pillar to ensure flexibility, scalability and technology-agnostic interactions among network infrastructure, operating systems and end-users. IBN aims to automate the service lifecycle, accelerating the deployment of communication services and advanced applications with multiple relevant Key

Performance Indicators (KPIs). IBN offers an abstraction layer that interprets and refines multiple intents (high-level requests) into specific network configurations and actions, considering service and operational demands [4]. Intent-based systems continuously ensure network performance and service quality by leveraging reliable system feedback.

However, the IBN's level of abstraction presents several challenges, such as i) how to effectively express intent in a human-friendly way, being capable of generalising several input attributes (e.g. different operators, number of users, network configurations and service types); ii) how to correctly interpret and translate the intent, sending it to the correct instance for execution; iii) how to guarantee reconciliation within the system, as per the intent assurance, refining the intents throughout its lifetime, considering the dynamism of networks, users and applications; and iv) how to handle inconsistencies, missing information or conflicting objectives.

To address these challenges, Artificial Intelligence (AI) models, including Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformers (BERT) and generative AI (GenAI) like Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT), Gemma, DeepSeek, the open-source Large Language Model Meta AI (LLaMA) and Mistral have emerged as powerful tools for improving the expression, interpretation and refinement of intents [5]–[8]. Nevertheless, an open challenge remains in determining which language model best ensures an optimal balance between complexity, performance and accessibility.

This work proposes a Language Model Intent-based Application Programming Interface (LM-IbAPI) for enhanced dynamic network management in B5G infrastructures. The proposal is an evolution of the Intent-based engine presented in our previous work [9] from Open-VERSO [10] and 6G-ENABERS-DLT projects [11], [12]. In this case, we implement a more flexible API with natural language composition to facilitate its use by several operators. The proposed LM-IbAPI is a logical layer that translates and delivers to specific South-bound Interfaces (SBIs), in a flexible and customised format, the different actions required by the 6GDIFERENTE¹ project's UCs. We evaluated several LMs (e.g. LLaMA, Mistral, Gemma) using Ollama, which provides a user-friendly and adaptable platform for leveraging the potential of these models at a local level [13].

¹<https://6gdiferente.com/>

The main contributions are: i) the LM-IbAPI implementation and integration with 6GDIFERENTE’s management layer to dynamically translate multiple intents from diverse domains into precise network actions/policies; ii) employing Ollama as a unified framework to easily access and compare several models, demonstrating that Mistral (*mistral_7B*) achieved the best trade-off between processing time and accuracy for our problem; iii) proper generalisation of high-level requests for different UCs, as well as accommodation of different attributes, such as number of users, service types, operators and contexts. For example, the model returns the SBI actions without the need for an additional module to classify the intent and preserving better situational and temporal awareness within the model.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the related works, including some theoretical fundamentals. Section III describes the considered UCs under the 6GDIFERENTE project. Next, Section IV presents the 6GDIFERENTE high-level architecture, where the LM-IbAPI is integrated, while Section V is devoted to the LM-IbAPI implementation and deployment. Section VI discusses the validation process and provides the corresponding results. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORKS

This Section covers some of the most recent standardisation efforts for IBN, as well as research related to LMs.

A. IBN Standardisation Efforts

The IBN paradigm has recently attracted increasing attention from the research community and several Standards Development Organisations (SDOs). The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) and the TeleManagement Forum (TMF), as well as open-source projects like CAMARA are actively contributing to defining and standardising the IBN paradigm [3], [4], [14].

For example, the TMF Intent-Driven Autonomous Networks (IDAN) framework [15] is oriented to telecommunication networks and delivers a set of standards covering multiple facets: (i) North-Bound Interface (NBI) APIs [16], which allows Create, Read, Update, and Delete (CRUD) operations on the intents, deliver intent reports events & negotiate by scaling/requesting approval, answer scaled intents, probe intents and remove these, deliver best intent and propose intent & deliver intent manager/registry; and (ii) intent models [17], [18] following the Resource Description Framework (RDF) structure and covering multiple attributes (e.g. targets and expectations). Specific workflows and other lifecycle management requirements are stated in other standards, part of the IDAN framework.

In [19], ETSI defines intent lifecycle phases on 5G Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) frameworks, discussing conflicts between intents, intent translation and testing. The IETF document [20] also provides a workflow for managing the IBN lifecycle, covering the traditional refinement with

other actions such as monitoring/observing and reporting on the intent status. Other IETF drafts like [21] apply the intent management from [20] to the 5G Software-Defined Vehicle (SDV) vertical, proposing a vehicular platform for Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) networking.

B. LM-Based Approaches

LM-IBN enables the conversion of human natural language into a structured and machine-readable format (e.g. JSON), ensuring consistency across diverse systems. Recent works have focused on deploying these LMs-based applied to different UCs and with different validation targets. In [22], Manias et al. proposed a Large Language Model (LLM) based on closed-source ChatGPT 3.5 for intent extraction in B5G core network operations. They presented several examples of 5G core intents and the prompting architecture components. However, they did not integrate the proposed model into a live 5G core testbed or prove other models to compare their performance.

The work [23] proposed an IBN framework based on GenAI models to support automated operations of B5G infrastructures with a special focus on the optical transport network. The performance of the proposed framework has been experimentally tested. In [24], the authors used Mistral for enhanced LLM-assisted IBN in the 5G core, promoting open-source models. Nevertheless, as also in [22], they did not evaluate the proposal performance with other state-of-the-art models.

Contrary, Fuad et al. [5] proposed an IBN framework based on LLMs, proving different models like GPT 3.5 and 4, Mistral and LLaMA 2. They explored the LLMs’ capabilities in BGP router and firewall configurations. They found that few-shot learning (i.e. training on a small subset of labelled examples) and prompt engineering (that is, iteratively improve the training input to find the best output) effectively generate correct firewall configurations. However, the scope of this investigation was limited to a few examples.

Bearing the previous research and standardisation efforts, this work proposed an IbAPI integrated with the management layer to handle multiple high-level intents from the 6GDIFERENTE project’s UCs and translate them into concise network actions. We also used few-shot learning and prompt engineering, providing specific guidelines and examples to improve the model performance. Using Ollama as a unified framework, we evaluated several LMs with different number of parameters like LLaMA 3, Mistral, Gemma 2, Qwen 2.5 and Phi-4. We compared them in terms of accuracy, number of wrong predictions and processing time.

III. USE CASES

The 6GDIFERENTE project proposes three UCs to showcase the capabilities from its connected infrastructures (Fig. 1, top). From these, two UCs were selected for this implementation. The requirements of such UCs, as Key Value Indicators (KVI), are considered during the design of the LM-IbAPI to adequately provide the expected features (Table I).

- 1) UC1 covers real-time transmission of volumetric video (e.g., for XR concerts), where artists are captured and

Table I: KVIs for the UCs

	UC1	UC2
Flexibility: interoperability	✓	-
Flexibility: resource usage	✓	✓
Inclusion: connected infrastructure	✓	✓
Privacy & trustworthiness	✓	-
Reliability: network visibility	✓	✓
Reliability: quality guarantees	✓	-
Sustainability: dynamic adaptability	✓	✓
Sustainability: efficient usage	✓	-
Ubiquitous access	✓	-

transmitted in a one-to-many fashion and where audience can also be captured and retransmitted in a many-to-many fashion within their selected communities. This requires the infrastructure to be setup and maintained in a manner such that it ensures low latency and jitter, reduced packet loss and high reliability.

- UC2 tackles the scenarios of (i) mobility across geographic areas, where a vehicle may lose terrestrial coverage and require switching to NTN; or (ii) offloading congested TNs to NTNs. Associated services in the edge must migrate across areas, routing must be adapted, and sessions must be transferred.

From the LM-IbAPI perspective, these KVIs are encoded as natural language sentences. They are part of the prompt engineering and may also be present in the end-user intent. The model must consider these sentences to generate the expected output. The output consists of arguments represented as keyword arguments, such as *key=value*.

IV. FRAMEWORK ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 shows, from the bottom-up, the 6GDIFERENTE high-level architecture composed of three main layers: infrastructure, management and service. The infrastructure layer corresponds to the equipment (i.e. Radio Access Network (RAN), core and edge cloud components) distributed across multiple sites and communicated through federated connections. Each infrastructure has its own container management system based on Kubernetes technology. Using this platform, the management layer can deploy and control different applications corresponding to the UCs defined in Section III.

The management layer is the core element in the 6GDIFERENTE framework. It is responsible for deploying and maintaining the different software modules for the execution of UCs in the infrastructure. This layer presents a Multi-Cloud Orchestrator in charge of aggregating the different orchestrators (ECCO & VINO and i2EDGE). Each orchestrator presents specific adapters to manage the corresponding Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) in the infrastructure layer. Further details about the orchestrator elements are out of the scope of this paper.

On the other hand, the Monitoring & Alerting framework analyses the metrics collected by Prometheus servers in the infrastructure layer. It triggers an alarm (reactive monitoring)

Fig. 1: High-level 6GDIFERENTE architecture

if the defined conditions in the Service Level Objective (SLO) Manager are not met. Additionally, it generates an alert (proactive monitoring) if it predicts some threshold violation. The consumers of these generated events can be the infrastructure operators, infrastructure orchestrators and UC control systems. This aligns with the ZSM and orchestration system’s autonomy principle. Another essential part of the management layer is the CAMARA Edge Cloud, situated explicitly in the Service API Manager (SAM) and connected through SBIs to the Multi-Cloud Orchestrator. CAMARA includes several standardised APIs such as services lifecycle management, the discovery of edge computing infrastructures, Quality on Demand (QoD) and connectivity insights [25]. The Registry is another critical element of the 6GDIFERENTE framework, where all physical types of equipment and their specific characteristics are registered.

On top of the 6GDIFERENTE architecture, the service layer presents specific applications to visualise the system’s collected data and operate infrastructure through the management layer. For the operation and deployment of network functions, the operator has a Graphical User Interface (GUI) which interacts directly with the API interfaces of the management layer.

The proposed LM-IbAPI is inserted into the described 6GDIFERENTE framework, specifically into the SAM. The LM-IbAPI aims to dynamically translate multiple intents from the service layer (s.t., the defined UCs) into network actions/policies to be executed by the CAMARA Edge Cloud, the Monitoring & Alerting framework (SLO) or the Registry

Table II: Some of the examples included at the system prompt (6GDIFERENTE’s UCs)

Prompt	Expected answer
Create a holoconference session with a maximum of 50 users with service migration between i2CAT and Vicomtech nodes	<create><holoconference><nodes=[i2cat, vicomtech], max_users=50, service_migration=True, SBI=CAMARA>
Setup alert-driven handover for i2CAT TN-NTN infrastructure with profile 4	<handover><ntn_tn><nodes=[i2cat], handover_mech=alerts, handover_mech_alert_profile=profile4, SBI=SLO>
Retrieve hardware that belongs to i2CAT	<retrieve><hardware><nodes=[i2cat], SBI=Registry>

Table III: LLMs used through the Ollama framework

Model	Parameters (B)	Open-Source	Quantisation (b)
Qwen2.5	14	Open-weight	4
Phi4	14	Open-weight	4
Gemma2	9	Open-weight	8
Mistral	7	Yes	4
Llama 3	8	Yes	4
Llama 3.1	8	Yes	4
Llama 3.2	3	Yes	4
Qwen2.5	32	Open-weight	4
Deepseek-coder	7	Yes	4

Fig. 2: Testbed deployment for the LM-IbAPI

entity. The implementation and deployment details will be covered in Section V.

V. DEPLOYMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. Deployment

Fig. 2 depicts the testbed architecture for evaluating LM-IbAPI performance with various LLMs. The pipeline operates as follows: Ollama², a framework for executing quantised LLMs, initially transforms a user’s natural language query into a structured, “semi-natural” language representation using a selected LLM. LM-IbAPI then applies a deterministic normalisation process, implemented in Python, to this intermediate representation. Table III details the LLMs tested, ranked by parameter count (billions, B) and describing its quantisation (bits, b). The Ollama instance (v0.4.4) runs on a virtual machine featuring an 8-core Intel Xeon (Cascadelake) processor (2.1 GHz), 32GB RAM and 300GB storage. GPU acceleration is provided by an NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU (15GB memory) in pass-through mode. We monitored and analyzed all Ollama

²<https://ollama.ai/>

interactions via Langfuse³, an open-source LLM observability platform.

B. Implementation

We used few-shot prompting, providing useful guidelines for structuring the outputs into action, resource and keyword arguments (<action><resource><keyword_args>).

Moreover, as Table II shows, we included some examples of each UC to allow the model to learn and provide the expected answers. The current version of the system prompt has undergone an iterative process to ensure the expected results, being the model capable of generalising considering different numbers of users, service types, operators and contexts. One crucial argument in the system is the SBI, ensuring that the system correctly identifies and handles the Service Binding Information. We specified at the system prompt the three valid values (CAMARA, SLO, Registry) and the necessity to always provide this information.

In this paper, we focused on UCs 1 and 2, extending their intent capabilities to include interactions with the Hardware Registry. This scope allowed us to thoroughly evaluate the system’s ability to interpret and execute a specific set of user intents.

To manage the flow of intent processing, we implemented a Finite-State Machine (FSM). This FSM ensures that user intents are handled systematically, from initial reception to execution or rejection. Upon receiving an intent, the system first determines its type (natural or semi-natural language) using a choice node within the FSM. The intent is then translated into the structured format specified in the prompt. A relevance check is performed and, if the intent is deemed relevant, it proceeds to execution; which includes handling the SBI parameter. The FSM transitions to an *Intent Enforced* state upon successful execution or an *Intent Rejection* state if execution fails or the intent is deemed irrelevant. This structure allows the system to be simple, yet easily changed and extended.

VI. VALIDATION

To validate the proposal, we generated a dataset with 154 samples of the described 6GDIFERENTE UCs, including the prompt (that it is the input text the LM receives) and expected response. Then, we ran the LMs presented in Table III and compared them regarding accuracy and processing time.

Table IV depicts the average processing time of each LM and the average processing time per intent expressed in

³<https://langfuse.com/>

Table IV: Average processing time (s) for several LMs

Model	Total processing time	Processing time per intent
<i>qwen25_14B</i>	343	2.23
<i>phi4_14B</i>	363	2.36
<i>gemma2_9B</i>	241.4	1.57
<i>llama3_8B</i>	194	1.26
<i>llama3.1_8B</i>	187.4	1.22
<i>mistral_7B</i>	176	1.14
<i>llama3.2_3B</i>	112	0.73

seconds (s). On the other hand, Table V shows the accuracy and Fig. 3 details the number of wrong predictions for different temperature (*temp*) values. The accuracy measures how well the LM translates high-level intents into the correct network actions. Specifically, *accuracy* = 100 % means that every generated network action is precisely what is expected for each given intent (i.e. no wrong predictions) [26].

For all models, except for *qwen25_14B*, results demonstrated that accuracy decreases as the *temp* increases because higher *temp* values generate more random and creative outputs, negatively impacting the output structure and accuracy [27]. In the case of *qwen25_14B*, it was able to correctly translate 100 % of the intents for all *temp* values, while *phi4_14B* presented the maximum accuracy for all considered temperature values except for *temp* = {0.7, 0.9}. However, as these LMs use 14B of parameters, they are more complex and heavier, negatively impacting the average processing time and, in general, the computational resources. For example, the average processing time of *phi4_14B* and *qwen25_14B* was 3.24 and 3.06 times greater, respectively, than the smallest LM we tested (*llama3.2_3B*). Additionally, *llama3.2_3B* presented the lowest average processing time but also the lowest accuracy among all analysed LMs (at least nine wrong predictions). Fig. 4 shows two screenshots from the Langfuse tool, evidencing two intents translated using *llama3.2_3B*. The first is a correct prediction, while the second is wrong. In this case, the error was that the SBI was wrongly predicted; instead of CAMARA, the model responded SLO.

Then, considering the analysed metrics, *mistral_7B* presented the best performance. With 7B of parameters, it guaranteed a processing time of 1.14 s per intent (51.7% and 48.9% less than *phi4_14B* and *qwen25_14B*, respectively) and *accuracy* = 100 % for all *temp* values, except for *temp* = 0.9 with only one wrong prediction.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposed a LM-IbAPI for enhanced dynamic network management in B5G infrastructures. Within the framework of the 6GDIFERENTE project, LM-IbAPI was integrated into the management layer to translate multiple intents into precise network actions/policies dynamically. We used Ollama as a unified platform to effectively test several LMs. We used few-shot prompting, providing valuable guidelines for structuring the outputs into action, resource and keyword arguments. We concluded that Mistral with 7 billion parameters (*mistral_7B*) achieved the best trade-off between accuracy and processing time among all evaluated models

Fig. 3: Number of wrong predictions for several LMs and different *temp* values

with no wrong predictions except for a temperature value of 0.9 (*accuracy* = 99.35%). The results demonstrated a good generalisation of high-level requests across different use cases, effectively accommodating attributes like the number of users, SBI and network contexts. As part of our future work, we aim to fine-tune the models to improve their performance while increasing the dataset size. Additionally, we plan to perform a hallucination-level analysis and incorporate evaluation metrics such as BLEU and ROUGE.

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Table V: Accuracy (%) for several LMs and different *temp* values

Model	<i>temp</i> = 0.1	<i>temp</i> = 0.3	<i>temp</i> = 0.5	<i>temp</i> = 0.7	<i>temp</i> = 0.9
<i>qwen25_14B</i>	100	100	100	100	100
<i>phi4_14B</i>	100	100	100	98.7	98.7
<i>gemma2_9B</i>	96.1	96.75	96.1	96.1	95.45
<i>llama3_8B</i>	96.1	96.1	96.1	94.81	94.81
<i>llama3.1_8B</i>	97.4	96.1	98.05	96.75	94.16
<i>mistral_7B</i>	100	100	100	100	99.35
<i>llama3.2_3B</i>	94.16	94.16	94.16	93.51	93.51

Fig. 4: Visualisation of two intent predictions using *llama3.2_3B*: (a) Correct, (b) Incorrect

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